

Impact of atmospheric boundary layer profiling

Chapter: Solar energy applications

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Authors	Main author: Florica Toanca – National Institute of Research and Development for Optoelectronics INOE, Romania Contributors: Claudia Acquistapace, University of Cologne, Germany Henri Diemoz, ARPA Valle d Aosta, Saint Christophe, Italy Jean-Francois Ribaud, CNR - Institut Pierre Simon LaPlace (IPSL), Palaiseau, France Martial Haeffelin, CNR - Institut Pierre Simon LaPlace (IPSL), Palaiseau, France

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1 Introduction

1.1 PROBE COST ACTION: Atmospheric Boundary Layer vs Solar Energy Applications

PROBE COST ACTION aimed to contribute specific tools and expertise for progressing beyond the state-of-the-art in each identified challenge by fostering cooperation and organizing the development of tools and products. One of the challenges addressed by PROBE was demonstrating the relevance of Atmospheric Boundary Layer (ABL) profiling for improving forecasts of various factors relevant to solar energy applications, including high-impact severe weather, poor air quality, renewable energy availability, and urban environment-specific needs. For solar energy applications, accurate forecasts of severe weather events are crucial for ensuring the reliability and safety of solar power systems. Severe weather such as storms, hurricanes, and heavy precipitation can damage solar panels and disrupt energy production. By incorporating ABL profiling into weather forecasting models, PROBE aimed to enhance the accuracy of severe weather predictions, allowing solar energy operators to better prepare for and mitigate the impacts of adverse weather conditions. Poor air quality can also affect the performance of solar panels by reducing the amount of sunlight reaching the Earth's surface. ABL profiling provides valuable data on atmospheric pollutants and their dispersion, enabling better forecasts of air quality conditions. By integrating ABL profiling into air quality monitoring and forecasting systems, PROBE sought to improve the prediction of air pollution episodes, helping solar energy operators anticipate periods of reduced solar radiation and adjust their operations accordingly. Furthermore, ABL profiling plays a crucial role in assessing renewable energy availability, particularly for solar energy. By characterizing the vertical structure of the atmosphere and monitoring parameters such as wind speed, temperature, and humidity, ABL profiling contributes to more accurate forecasts of solar irradiance and energy production potential. PROBE aimed to leverage ABL profiling data to enhance renewable energy forecasting models, enabling better estimation of solar energy generation, and supporting the efficient integration of solar power into the grid. Finally, understanding urban environment-specific needs is essential for optimizing the deployment of solar energy systems in urban areas. ABL profiling provides valuable insights into the microclimatic conditions and atmospheric dynamics within urban environments, which influence the performance and efficiency of solar installations. By integrating ABL profiling data with urban planning and energy management strategies, PROBE aimed to support the development of solar energy solutions tailored to the unique characteristics of urban settings, ultimately promoting the adoption of sustainable energy technologies in cities.

An essential objective of the PROBE COST ACTION was to actively involve stakeholders from five diverse categories (Academia, Industry, Operational agencies, Sustained research structures, End-users) with an emphasis on end-users who leverage solar radiation for multiple purposes. By prioritizing engagement with end-users, the initiative aims to ensure that its endeavors are intricately aligned with the practical needs and requirements of those directly impacted by solar radiation applications. This inclusive approach not only fosters collaboration and knowledge exchange but also facilitates the tailoring of project outputs to effectively address the specific challenges and opportunities encountered by end-users in harnessing solar radiation for their respective endeavors.

According to deliverable 1.1: List of identified relevant stakeholders, throughout the action, potential stakeholders were identified and invited to join PROBE activities. Attractive information material was considered an important mean to demonstrate the benefits of PROBE ACTION activities to the stakeholders. Based on feedback from the stakeholders, user needs were identified, reviewed, and defined.

1.2 Importance of Atmospheric Boundary Layer Profiling in Solar Energy Applications

The atmospheric boundary layer (ABL), the lowest portion of the Earth's atmosphere, is a dynamic zone where interactions between the Earth's surface and the overlying atmosphere play a crucial role in shaping weather patterns and climate dynamics (Kotthaus et al, 2018a, 2018b, 2020). ABL profiling offers valuable insights into the vertical structure and characteristics of this layer, providing essential information for optimizing solar energy systems.

1.2 Factors Affecting Solar Energy Generation

Solar energy generation is subject to various atmospheric phenomena that can significantly impact its availability and efficiency. Among these factors, cloud cover, fog, and aerosols emerge as primary influencers, modulating the amount and distribution of incoming solar radiation. Understanding the

dynamics of these atmospheric components is essential for accurately assessing solar resource potential and devising effective energy management strategies.

"Solar Engineering of Thermal Processes" by Duffie and Beckman, 2013 serves as a foundational text, exploring diverse elements such as solar radiation, atmospheric conditions, and system design considerations. It provides a comprehensive review focusing on solar energy conversion efficiency, elucidating the impacts of solar irradiance, temperature, shading, tilt angle, and module technology. Other studies evaluate the photovoltaic potential in Europe, considering geographical distribution, intensity, and diurnal variation, with a keen focus on solar irradiance, temperature, and shading effects. Together, these papers contribute to a deeper understanding of the intricate interplay between environmental, technological, and geographical factors shaping solar energy generation.

1.3 Solar Energy Deployment in the European Union: Assessing Progress and Challenges

The "Renewable Energy Progress Report 2020" is a comprehensive publication produced by the European Commission, aimed at evaluating the advancement of European Union (EU) member states in achieving renewable energy targets set forth in various EU directives and agreements. This report serves as a vital tool for policymakers, industry stakeholders, and researchers to assess the state of renewable energy deployment across the EU, with a specific focus on solar energy. At its core, the report meticulously examines the progress made by EU member states in integrating renewable energy sources into their energy systems, with a particular emphasis on solar energy. It offers a detailed analysis of solar capacity installations, tracking the growth trends, geographical distribution, and technological advancements within the solar sector across different member states. By providing up-to-date data and statistics on solar capacity additions, the report enables stakeholders to gauge the effectiveness of policies and initiatives aimed at promoting solar energy adoption.

The solar energy sector has become a very dynamic and competitive industry, ensuring a constant output of innovative technologies. The EU has one of the strongest innovation environments across all solar energy technologies, from PV to concentrated solar power (CSP). The challenge now is to ensure that a new generation of breakthrough technologies leads to higher conversion efficiencies (which translate into less use of resources, such as space, raw materials, water, etc), increased circularity in the use of raw materials and a more sustainable life cycle, including in manufacturing

Through Horizon Europe, the EU will continue to support research and innovation to reduce the cost of solar energy technologies, while increasing their energy efficiency and their sustainability, including in the manufacturing stage. These new technologies include heterojunction cells, perovskites, and tandem cells, all of which achieve higher efficiencies than commercial technologies. Financial support is also needed for innovation in solar thermal or CSP technologies, as well as products tailored to innovative forms of deployment. The upcoming 2023-2024 work programme will include a flagship initiative to support solar energy research and innovation, focused inter alia on novel technologies, environmental and socio-economic sustainability, and integrated design. (<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=COM%3A2022%3A221%3AFIN&qid=1653034500503>)

The EU solar generation capacity keeps increasing and reached, according to Solar Power Europe, an estimated 259.99 GW in 2023. The EU has long been a front-runner in the roll-out of solar energy. Under the European Green Deal and the Repower EU plan, solar power is a building block of the EU's transition to cleaner energy. Its accelerated deployment contributes to reducing the EU's dependence on imported fossil fuels. In addition, solar energy is the most accessible renewable energy for households and contributes to protecting consumers from volatile energy prices. (https://energy.ec.europa.eu/topics/renewable-energy/solar-energy_en)

The "Renewable Energy Progress Report 2020," crafted by the European Commission, stands as a pivotal document evaluating the strides of European Union (EU) member states towards meeting renewable energy targets, with a focal point on solar energy. This comprehensive report serves as an indispensable resource for policymakers, industry players, and researchers, offering a nuanced examination of the integration of renewable energy sources, notably solar energy, into the EU's energy landscape.

At its essence, the report meticulously dissects the advancements made by EU member states in incorporating solar energy sources into their energy portfolios. It meticulously analyzes solar capacity installations, unveiling growth patterns, geographical spread, and technological innovations within the solar sector across diverse member states. By furnishing up-to-the-minute data and statistics on solar capacity expansions, the report equips stakeholders with the tools to evaluate the efficacy of policies and endeavors geared towards fostering solar energy adoption.

The solar energy sector within the EU emerges as a dynamic and fiercely competitive industry, characterized by a constant stream of innovative technologies. Notably, the EU boasts one of the most robust innovation environments across all solar energy domains, spanning from Photovoltaics (PV) to Concentrated Solar Power (CSP). The current challenge lies in harnessing a new wave of breakthrough technologies to drive higher conversion efficiencies, thereby reducing resource usage, enhancing circularity in raw material utilization, and fostering a more sustainable life cycle, especially in manufacturing processes.

Through Horizon Europe, the EU remains steadfast in its commitment to bolster research and innovation aimed at slashing the costs of solar energy technologies while amplifying their energy efficiency and sustainability, particularly in manufacturing realms. Novel technologies such as heterojunction cells, perovskites, and tandem cells stand poised to achieve greater efficiencies compared to commercial counterparts. Financial backing is imperative to fuel innovation in solar thermal or CSP technologies and to develop products tailored to innovative deployment methodologies. The forthcoming 2023-2024 work program is slated to feature a flagship initiative dedicated to fostering solar energy research and innovation, centering on novel technologies, environmental and socio-economic sustainability, and integrated design.

With the EU's solar generation capacity steadily climbing, reaching an estimated 259.99 GW in 2023 according to SolarPower Europe, the region continues to lead the charge in solar energy proliferation. Anchored by the European Green Deal and the REPowerEU plan, solar power serves as a cornerstone of the EU's transition towards cleaner energy sources. Its accelerated deployment not only curtails the EU's reliance on imported fossil fuels but also democratizes access to renewable energy for households, shielding consumers from volatile energy prices.

In conjunction with the meticulous assessment of solar energy deployment in the European Union, boundary layer studies play a crucial role in optimizing solar energy applications. Understanding the dynamics of the atmospheric boundary layer is paramount in comprehending the complex interplay between atmospheric phenomena and solar energy generation. By delving into boundary layer studies, researchers can gain valuable insights into how factors such as cloud cover, aerosols, and atmospheric turbulence influence solar irradiance and energy availability. These studies provide essential data on the vertical structure and characteristics of the atmosphere, enabling more accurate forecasts of solar irradiance and energy production potential. By integrating boundary layer data into solar energy modeling and forecasting systems, stakeholders can enhance the efficiency and reliability of solar energy systems, ultimately contributing to the broader goal of transitioning towards a sustainable energy future.

1.4 Purpose and Structure of the Deliverable

This deliverable aims to explore the intricate relationship between atmospheric boundary layer profiling and solar energy applications, delving into the specific effects of cloud cover, fog, and aerosols on solar energy generation. Through a comprehensive examination of relevant research findings, case studies, and practical considerations, this document seeks to provide valuable insights for researchers, engineers, policymakers, and industry stakeholders involved in the design, implementation, and operation of solar energy systems. The structure of the Deliverable will be the following: Introduction; Cloud Cover; Fog Alerts; Aerosol Extinction Profiles; Aerosol Radiative Effects; Conclusions, References.

2 Cloud cover: exploring the influence of cloud dynamics on solar energy generation

In the context of solar energy generation, understanding the dynamics of the atmospheric boundary layer is paramount, particularly concerning its interaction with cloud cover. Clouds, with their diverse forms and behaviors, exert a profound influence on solar radiation reaching the Earth's surface, thereby significantly impacting the performance and efficiency of solar energy systems. This chapter delves into the intricate relationship between cloud dynamics and solar energy generation, exploring the multifaceted effects of cloud cover on solar irradiance, diffuse radiation, and overall energy availability. By elucidating the complex interplay between cloud dynamics and solar energy generation, this chapter aims to provide valuable insights for optimizing the design, operation, and management of solar energy systems in varying atmospheric conditions.

2.1 Explanation of cloud cover and its impact on solar energy availability

Cloud cover is a dynamic phenomenon that changes throughout the day and across different geographical locations. Monitoring and forecasting cloud cover are essential for optimizing the design, operation, and performance of solar energy systems (Long & Ackerman, 2000). Advanced weather forecasting techniques, satellite imagery, and ground-based observations are employed to assess cloud cover patterns and anticipate its impact on solar energy availability (Illingworth et al., 2007). Additionally, integrating energy storage systems and hybrid renewable energy technologies can mitigate the variability of solar energy generation caused by cloud cover, ensuring a more reliable and stable energy supply.

One of the main instruments for cloud profiling within the Atmospheric Boundary Layer (ABL) is the Cloud Radar (CR), operating either at 35 or 94 GHz (Illingworth et al., 2007). The use of ceilometers (ALC) is also extended within the cloud profiling community. The synergy of Cloud Radars with ceilometers and Microwave Radiometers (MWRs) is a powerful tool for the study of cloud properties' vertical distribution (Hogan et al., 2007). Combined databases of these instruments are usually used in existing retrieval algorithms. Many stations within Europe continuously report within the CLOUDNET network (<https://cloudnet.fmi.fi/>) as part of ACTRIS, which combines Cloud Radars, ceilometers, and MWRs for the detection, classification, and retrieval of cloud properties (Illingworth et al., 2007).

2.2 Importance of accurate cloud cover prediction for solar energy planning and forecasting

Accurate prediction of cloud cover is paramount for effective solar energy planning and forecasting. Clouds significantly influence solar irradiance levels, directly impacting the amount of energy that solar photovoltaic (PV) systems can generate. Therefore, precise forecasts of cloud cover allow solar energy stakeholders, such as utilities, grid operators, and renewable energy developers, to anticipate fluctuations in solar energy output and plan accordingly (Long & Ackerman, 2000). For example, utilities can use cloud cover forecasts to optimize the integration of solar energy into the grid, ensuring reliable and stable electricity supply while minimizing the need for backup power sources. Similarly, renewable energy developers rely on accurate cloud cover predictions to optimize the siting and sizing of solar installations, maximizing energy production and project profitability (Illingworth et al., 2007).

Moreover, accurate cloud cover prediction plays a crucial role in short-term and long-term solar energy forecasting. Short-term forecasts, spanning hours to days, are essential for real-time energy management and grid balancing, allowing operators to adjust generation and consumption to match fluctuating solar output. Long-term forecasts, covering weeks to months, are vital for strategic planning, investment decisions, and policy formulation in the renewable energy sector. By providing reliable insights into future cloud cover patterns, accurate predictions enable stakeholders to make informed decisions regarding solar energy deployment, infrastructure investments, and energy transition strategies. In this way, the importance of accurate cloud cover prediction extends beyond immediate operational considerations to shaping the trajectory of the renewable energy transition and achieving sustainable energy goals.

2.3 Techniques for measuring and predicting cloud cover, including satellite imagery, ground-based observations, and numerical weather prediction models

Various techniques are employed to measure and predict cloud cover, encompassing satellite imagery, ground-based observations, and numerical weather prediction models. Satellite-based platforms, equipped with advanced sensors, provide comprehensive coverage and high-resolution imagery for monitoring cloud dynamics on a global scale. These satellites capture data across different wavelengths, allowing for the detection of various cloud types, their spatial distribution, and temporal evolution. Ground-based instruments, such as sky cameras and pyranometers, offer localized observations of cloud cover and solar irradiance (Long & Ackerman, 2000). Sky cameras capture continuous images of the sky, enabling the analysis of cloud types, coverage, and movement patterns over specific locations. Pyranometers measure solar irradiance levels, facilitating the assessment of cloud impact on solar energy availability (Wang et al., 2017; T. Mathijssen, W. Knap, 2021). Additionally, numerical weather prediction models integrate meteorological data to simulate cloud formation and movement, enabling short- to long-term cloud cover forecasts.

Combining data from satellite observations, ground-based instruments, and numerical weather prediction models enhances the accuracy and reliability of cloud cover prediction. Satellite imagery provides a broad overview of cloud cover patterns, while ground-based observations offer detailed insights into local cloud dynamics and solar irradiance levels. Numerical weather prediction models complement these observations by simulating atmospheric processes and interactions, enabling the

projection of cloud cover changes over different spatial and temporal scales. By integrating multiple data sources and analytical techniques, meteorologists and climate scientists can develop comprehensive cloud cover prediction systems that support various applications, including weather forecasting, climate modeling, and solar energy planning (Hogan et al., 2003; Stull, 1988). These prediction systems play a crucial role in mitigating the impacts of weather-related events, optimizing renewable energy utilization, and supporting sustainable development efforts worldwide.

2.4 Case studies demonstrating the influence of cloud cover variability on solar energy generation

In the context of "Cloud cover: exploring the influence of cloud dynamics on solar energy generation" and its relation to "Impact of atmospheric boundary layer profiling on solar energy applications," the paper "Prediction of Short-Time Cloud Motion Using a Deep-Learning Model" by Xinyue Su et al. assumes significance. This study's deep learning model for short-term cloud motion prediction holds promise for enhancing the accuracy of solar energy generation forecasts by accounting for cloud dynamics. By integrating insights from atmospheric boundary layer profiling and cloud motion prediction, solar energy systems can better anticipate and adapt to fluctuations in cloud cover, ultimately optimizing energy production and resource management in renewable energy applications.

Exploring the intricacies of solar energy generation requires a comprehensive understanding of the atmospheric conditions influencing cloud dynamics. In a recent study (Pîrloagă et. al, 2022) Data collected over a period of 18 months (December 2019–May 2021) at the Bucharest–Măgurele Cloudnet station were analyzed for the first time to determine the macrophysical and microphysical cloud properties over this site. A total number of 1,327,680 vertical profiles containing the target classification based on the Cloudnet algorithm were analysed, of which 1,077,858 profiles contained hydrometeors. The highest number of profiles with hydrometeors (>60%) was recorded in December 2020, with hydrometeors being observed mainly below 5 km. Above 5 km, the frequency of occurrence of hydrometeors was less than <20%. Based on the initial Cloudnet target classification, a cloud classification scheme was implemented. Clouds were more frequently observed during winter compared with other seasons (45% of all profiles). Ice clouds were the most frequent type of cloud (468,463 profiles) during the study period, followed by mixed phases (220,280 profiles) and mixed phased precipitable clouds (164,868 profiles). The geometrical thickness varied from a median value of 244 m for liquid clouds during summer to 3362 m for mix phased precipitable clouds during spring.

Figure 1: The Cloudnet target classification and the hydrometeors and cloud classification used in this study. The cloud classification is adapted from Achtert, P.; O'Connor, E.J.; Brooks, I.M.; Sotiropoulou, G.; Shupe, M.D.; Pospichal, B.; Brooks, B.J.; Tjernström, M. Properties of Arctic liquid and mixed-phase clouds from shipborne Cloudnet observations during ACSE 2014. *Atmos. Chem. Phys.* 2020, 20, 14983–15002.

Figure 2: Frequency of occurrence for (a) liquid, mixed-phase, and ice hydrometeors, (b) ice hydrometeors, (c) mixed-phase hydrometeors, and (d) liquid hydrometeors identified using the method proposed by [19] and based on target classification data from Cloudnet. The values are normalized to the total number of profiles for each month. The red dotted rectangle indicates the months with incomplete data (as shown in Figure 5). Left panels show the monthly distribution by altitude, and the right panels show the seasonal distribution by altitude. (Pirloagă et al, 2023)

These findings hold significant implications for solar energy planning and forecasting efforts, as they underscore the need for robust methodologies to incorporate cloud variability into predictive models. By integrating ground-based measurements of cloud properties into solar energy planning processes, stakeholders can develop more accurate forecasts and optimize the design and operation of solar energy systems to maximize efficiency and reliability. Additionally, the insights gleaned from this study underscore the importance of ongoing research in understanding the complex interactions between cloud dynamics and solar energy generation, ultimately driving advancements in renewable energy technology, and facilitating the transition towards a sustainable energy future.

3 Fog alerts: investigating the impact of fog events on solar energy systems

According to the World Meteorological Organization (2021), fog occurs when visibility at the Earth's surface is lower than 1 km due to the presence of suspended water droplets. Fog has a significant socioeconomic impact, e.g. through its effects on road traffic, rescue management or severe disruptions at airports, including delays or even cancellations of flights (Gultepe et al., 2009). In semi-arid and arid regions also, fog can constitute a fundamental resource as it can supply water to the local population. Therefore, accurate forecasting of fog events is essential. An improved version of the near-real-time decision tool PARAFOG (PFG2) has been implemented at 10 European sites (incl., Paris, Munich, Zurich, Vienna, Burgas, Ljubljana, Uccle) (Haefelin et al. 2016; Ribaud et al. 2021). This tool provides pre-fog alert levels and discriminates between radiation (RAD) and stratus lowering (STL) fog situations. PFG2 has two distinct modules to monitor the physical processes involved in RAD and STL fog formation. The modules are based on innovative fuzzy logic algorithms to retrieve fog alert levels (low, moderate, high) specific to RAD/STL conditions, minutes to hours prior to fog onset. The PFG2-RAD module also assesses the thickness of the fog. Both the PFG2-RAD and PFG2-STL modules rely on the combination of visibility observations and ALC measurements.

Figure 3: Time series presenting measurements and the corresponding retrieved alert level outputs from PARAFOG in operational mode during a thick radiation fog formation on 30–31 October 2015 at SIRTA. (a) visibility, (b) ALC-attenuated backscatter between 0 and 400 m (color contours), together with the altitude of the maximum gradient (black points), (c) alert levels retrieved from PFG2, and (d) fog type and PARAFOG status. Adapted from Ribaud et al. (2021).

At all sites, pre-fog alert levels retrieved by PFG2 are found to be consistent with the local weather analysis. The advanced PFG2 algorithm performs with a hit rate of about 100 % for both considered fog types and presents a false alarm ratio on the order of 10 % (30 %) for RAD (STL) fog situations. The first high alerts that result in a subsequent fog event are found to occur for periods of time ranging from –120 min to fog onset, with the first high alerts occurring earlier for RAD than STL cases. There are not yet any products available for the anticipation of fog dissipation. Nevertheless, several studies have highlighted the importance of having a strong instrumental synergy in remote sensing (DCR, MWR, DL) to monitor the processes involved in the fog life cycle. Thanks to these results, various activities are under way for the development of tools to assess and forecast fog dissipation

4 Aerosol extinction profiles: analyzing aerosol distribution and its implications for solar radiation

Analyzing aerosol extinction profiles provides crucial insights into aerosol distribution and its implications for solar radiation, a fundamental consideration in solar energy exploration and utilization. Aerosols, comprising suspended particulate matter and pollutants in the atmosphere, exert a profound influence on the transmission, scattering, and absorption of solar radiation, thus significantly modulating both the quantity and quality of solar energy reaching the Earth's surface (Seinfeld & Pandis, 2016). By delving into aerosol extinction profiles, researchers can unravel the intricate spatial and temporal distribution patterns of aerosols, shedding light on their vertical structure and optical properties and, consequently, their impact on solar energy availability.

Studies focusing on aerosol extinction profiles leverage various measurement techniques, including lidar, sun photometry, and satellite observations, to capture comprehensive vertical profiles of aerosol concentration and optical characteristics (Dubovik et al., 2002). These profiles offer valuable insights into the complex interplay between aerosols and solar radiation. For instance, detailed analyses of aerosol vertical distribution highlight the presence of distinct aerosol layers and their varying optical thicknesses, crucial for understanding their attenuation and scattering effects on solar irradiance. Moreover, investigations into aerosol extinction profiles enable researchers to identify sources of aerosol pollution, track their transport and dispersion patterns, and assess their contributions to regional and global atmospheric dynamics and climate change. By elucidating these complex aerosol-radiation interactions, research on aerosol extinction profiles not only advances our understanding of atmospheric processes but also informs the development of more accurate solar energy forecasting models and the optimization of solar energy systems for improved efficiency and reliability.

4.1 Aerosol Extinction Profiles

Aerosols, tiny suspended particles in the atmosphere, play a crucial role in modulating solar radiation transmission and influencing the performance of solar energy systems. This chapter explores the concept of aerosol extinction profiles, their characteristics, and their implications for solar energy applications. Aerosol extinction profiles represent the vertical distribution of aerosol concentration and their attenuation of solar radiation with altitude. These profiles provide valuable information about the spatial and temporal variability of aerosol particles in the atmosphere, which can significantly impact the amount and quality of solar radiation reaching the Earth's surface.

4.2 Importance of Aerosol Extinction Profiles for Solar Energy

Aerosols scatter and absorb solar radiation, leading to changes in the spectral distribution and intensity of sunlight. Understanding aerosol extinction profiles is essential for accurately assessing solar irradiance levels and predicting solar energy generation potential. Moreover, aerosols can influence atmospheric stability, cloud formation, and weather patterns, further emphasizing the need to incorporate aerosol data into solar energy planning and forecasting models (Dubovik & King, 2000).

4.3 Techniques for Measuring Aerosol Extinction Profiles

Various techniques are employed to measure aerosol extinction profiles, ranging from ground-based lidar and sun photometer observations to satellite remote sensing and aircraft-based measurements. These techniques provide valuable insights into aerosol properties such as size distribution, composition, and vertical distribution, enabling researchers to characterize aerosol optical properties and their impact on solar energy (Dubovik & King, 2000).

4.4 Case Studies Demonstrating the Influence of Aerosol Extinction Profiles on Solar Energy Generation

Case studies offer empirical evidence of how aerosol extinction profiles affect solar energy generation in different regions and under varying atmospheric conditions. By analyzing aerosol data alongside solar irradiance measurements, researchers can quantify the relationship between aerosol loading, atmospheric transparency, and solar energy availability. These case studies provide valuable insights into the regional variability of aerosol effects on solar energy and highlight the importance of accounting for aerosol properties in solar energy resource assessment and forecasting (Dubovik & King, 2000).

5 Aerosol radiative effects: assessing the role of aerosols in modulating solar energy fluxes

Aerosols can scatter and absorb solar radiation, leading to modifications in the amount, distribution, and spectral properties of incoming sunlight reaching the Earth's surface. Understanding the radiative effects of aerosols is crucial for comprehensively assessing their impact on climate change, air quality, and renewable energy resources. This review focuses on elucidating the diverse radiative effects of aerosols and their implications for solar radiation, drawing insights from recent research findings and methodological advancements in the field. By examining the complex interactions between aerosols and solar radiation, this review aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of aerosol radiative effects and their role in shaping Earth's climate system.

Over the years, numerous studies have investigated the diverse effects of aerosols on solar radiation, ranging from regional-scale assessments to global-scale analyses. These studies employ a variety of observational, experimental, and modelling approaches to quantify the magnitude and spatial variability of aerosol radiative effects and their implications for solar energy fluxes. By elucidating the complex relationship between aerosols and solar radiation, researchers aim to improve our understanding of aerosol-cloud-climate interactions and inform strategies for sustainable energy planning, climate adaptation, and environmental management. This review provides an overview of recent advancements in the study of aerosol radiative effects, highlighting key findings, methodologies, and future research directions in this interdisciplinary field.

Bond et al. 2013 provides a comprehensive assessment of the role of black carbon aerosols in the climate system. It examines the impact of black carbon on radiative forcing and its contribution to climate change, offering important insights into the role of aerosols in shaping Earth's climate.

Fasano et al. (2021): This publication investigates the vertical profile of the clear-sky aerosol direct radiative effect in an Alpine valley. By combining ground-based measurements and radiative transfer simulations, the study provides insights into how aerosols affect solar radiation within mountainous regions, contributing to our understanding of aerosol-radiation interactions in complex terrain.

6 Conclusions

In conclusion, the PROBE COST ACTION has made significant strides in engaging stakeholders from diverse backgrounds and aligning project activities with the practical needs of end-users in the field of solar energy applications. Through active stakeholder involvement, feedback collection, and tailored project design, the initiative has fostered collaboration and knowledge exchange, ultimately enhancing the relevance and impact of its endeavors. Moreover, the comprehensive exploration of atmospheric boundary layer profiling and its significance for solar energy applications underscores the critical role of accurate atmospheric characterization in optimizing solar energy systems and maximizing energy generation efficiency.

The examination of factors affecting solar energy generation, including cloud cover, fog, and aerosols, highlights the complex interplay between atmospheric dynamics and solar radiation availability. By elucidating the mechanisms underlying these phenomena and exploring advanced measurement and prediction techniques, stakeholders can better anticipate and mitigate the variability of solar energy generation, ultimately ensuring a more reliable and sustainable energy supply.

Furthermore, case studies presented within this deliverable demonstrate the practical implications of atmospheric boundary layer profiling and aerosol characterization for solar energy planning and forecasting. These studies provide empirical evidence of how atmospheric conditions influence solar energy generation, informing the development of more accurate prediction models and optimizing the design and operation of solar energy systems.

Overall, the insights gained from this deliverable contribute to a deeper understanding of the intricate relationship between atmospheric dynamics and solar energy generation, laying the groundwork for informed decision-making, technological innovation, and policy development in the renewable energy sector. By continuing to advance research, collaboration, and stakeholder engagement, the PROBE COST ACTION aims to drive progress towards a more sustainable and resilient energy future.

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